

Evaluation of jute-fibre based wetted pads in evaporative cooling operations

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Abstract : Jute woven and non-woven fabric of different area density (gsm) were evaluated in a designed and fabricated evaporatively cooled chamber of one cubic meter capacity. Physical properties and dimensions of these pads were evaluated before using it in the experimental setup. The water absorbancy value of jute non-woven pads was found higher than that of woven pads of same area density, same trend also observed in case of porosity values. At a particular pressure drop, the air permeability value decreases with increase in area density both for woven and non-woven pads. The highest cooling effect as a measure of maximum temperature drop and highest increase in relative humidity was observed in the case of woven cooling pads of 400 gsm in forced ventilation conditions. For a particular pad material, keeping the area density constant, the cooling effect in forced ventilation condition was found higher than that of natural ventilation conditions.

Keywords : Jute fibre, evaporation, permeability, humidification.

Introduction

Evaporative cooling is generally accepted to be an adiabatic humidification process¹. This process takes place when unsaturated air is brought into contact with a free water surface in the absence of other sources of heat. Water evaporates into the air stream resulting in a drop in the air dry bulb temperature due to sensible heat removal while the humidity and latent heat content of the air increases. Evaporative cooled (EC) storage structures can be utilized in places where the fresh perishable commodities are readily spoiled by high temperature and low relative humidity². It is not a competitor of the refrigerated storages and the quality of the produce stored in the EC chamber should not be compared with that in refrigerated storages. In the EC structures, we cannot maintain a temperature, which is optimum for storage of any particular commodity; rather, we try to take the maximum advantage of the natural environment by manipulating the ambient air and bringing down the temperature to a considerable low level. EC system consists of a pad (moist material), storage cabin, and an air pump (fan or natural breeze). The pad is the most important component of the system as temperature and humidity changes takes place there. A good pad material should be porous enough to allow free flow of air to effect evaporation. It should be

locally available and inexpensive and should easily be constructed into the required shape. Keeping in view of the above, pads prepared from jute woven and non-woven fabric of different specifications was evaluated in an designed and fabricated evaporatively cooled chamber of one cubic meter capacity.

Results and discussion

Physical properties :

The physical properties such as pad thickness, bulk density, porosity, air permeability and water absorbancy are presented in Table 1.

The porosity value of non-woven samples is higher than that of the woven sample at a particular fabric area density. The highest porosity (92.69%) was found in the case of non-woven fabric of 600 gsm and the lowest value (64.56%) was observed in the case of woven fabric of 600 gsm.

For a particular area density (gsm), the porosity of non-woven fabric is higher than that of woven fabric. This is because; the entanglement of fibre is not so strong in non-woven fabric resulting the large void space inside it. The void so created allows free air to make it porous resulting high porosity values.

Table 1. Physical properties of cooling pad

Sample	Area density (gsm)	Pad thickness (mm)	Weight (g)	Bulk density (g/cc)	Porosity (%)	Air permeability (Cc/cm ² /s)	Water absorbancy (%)
Non-woven		2.11	20.401	0.107			
	200	1.45	16.612	0.127	92.35	47.33	325.78
		1.71	15.331	0.099			
Non-woven	400	3.79	36.907	0.108	91.65	19.72	415.51
		4.07	40.836	0.111			
		2.76	36.380	0.146			
Non-woven	600	4.03	38.739	0.106	92.69	11.44	498.60
		3.93	40.620	0.114			
		4.44	39.928	0.099			
Woven	200	0.762	15.392	0.224	85.65	189.34	12.75
		0.815	14.812	0.201			
		0.787	14.130	0.199			
Woven	400	0.980	38.844	0.440	71.17	17.88	34.05
		0.965	35.175	0.405			
		0.965	35.618	0.410			
Woven	600	1.200	47.091	0.436	64.56	1.18	78.75
		1.215	61.456	0.562			
		1.157	56.787	0.545			

Air permeability :

At a particular pressure drop, the air permeability values decreases with increase in area density both for woven and non-woven pads. The air permeability at 1 mm wg pressure drop for non-woven pads of 200, 400 and 600 gsm are 47.33, 19.72 and 11.44 Cc/cm²/s respectively. For woven pads of 200, 400 and 600 gsm the values observed are 189.34, 17.88 and 1.18 Cc/cm²/s.

The air permeability drops down with the increase of fabric area density (gsm) for both woven and non-woven samples. It may be due to the fact that the fabric samples attain more compact structure with increase in area density in both the cases and thereby, resist the air flow through them.

Water absorbancy :

The water absorbancy value of jute non-woven pads were found higher than that of woven pads of same area density. The water absorbancy for non-woven pads of 200, 400 and 600 gsm are 325.78, 415.51 and 498.60% respectively. For woven pads of 200, 400 and 600 gsm

the values observed are 12.75, 34.05 and 78.75%.

It is evident from the results that, water absorption capacity of non-woven fabric is considerably higher than that of woven fabric. This is due to the fact that, number of pores present in the non-woven fabric is considerably more due to its inherent structure. And also the non-woven fabric is more voluminous than the woven sample because of its higher thickness.

Evaluation of cooling pads :

The cooling performance studies of pads prepared from jute woven and non-woven fabrics of different specifications was carried out in the designed and fabricated chamber both in the natural ventilation and forced ventilation conditions. The evaluation was made in the basis of reduction in temperature and increase in relative humidity. The values obtained are shown in from Figs. 1-4. The highest cooling effect as a measure of maximum temperature drop (10.3 °C) and maximum increase in relative humidity (31%) was observed in the case of woven cooling pads of 400 gsm in forced ventilation conditions.

Note

Fig. 1. Cooling performance of jute woven pads (forced ventilation)

Fig. 2. Cooling performance of jute non-woven pads (forced ventilation)

Fig. 3. Cooling performance of jute woven pads (natural ventilation)

Fig. 4. Cooling performance of jute non-woven pads (natural ventilation).

Experimental

Sample preparation :

Jute woven and non-woven fabric of different area density were procured from M/s Gloster Jute Mills Ltd., Kolkata. Cooling pads (size 1 m² × 1 m²) were prepared from this fabric to test in the experimental setup. For physical properties studies, the fabrics were cut into the required size.

Design and development of experimental setup :

An evaporative cooling chamber of 1 m³ capacity was designed and fabricated to test the cooling performance of pads. The top of the chamber was covered with a metallic tray to hold water. To moisten the pad material, a perforated pipe with flow regulation was attached to the holding tank. To collect the excess water flowing from the pad material, at bottom, a container was attached. The suction of air through the pads was achieved by the exhaust fan placed at the opposite end to the pad material. The pad material for testing was fixed with the help of fixing stand at the front side and the readings (temperature and relative humidity) was taken both inside and outside of the experimental setup. The testing of the cooling pads was carried out both at the natural and forced ventilation conditions.

Measurement of physical properties :

The bulk volume was computed using the physical dimensions of the samples viz. length, width and thickness. Bulk density of samples was computed dividing the weight of the cooling pads by their volume. The true den-

sity of the fibre was taken as 1.45 g/cc for calculation of the porosity values. The porosity or the packing factor of cooling pads of different specifications was computed using the following formula (Mohsenin, 1980) and expressed in the percentage values.

$$\text{Porosity or packing factor } \epsilon = (\tau - \rho) \times 100/\tau$$

where, ϵ = porosity or the packing factor, τ and ρ are true and bulk density of jute fibre and cooling pad respectively.

Measurement of air permeability :

Evaluation of air permeability of both woven and non-woven pads was conducted, using the Shirley Air Permeability Tester (SDL 21). The results have been expressed as the units of volume of air in cm³, flowing per second, through 1 cm² of fabric at a pressure difference of 10 mm_w or 1 cm head of water. Air permeability value was calculated by dividing the flow rate reading in cm³/s at 1 cm pressure head of water by the test area, which in this instrument is 5.07 cm².

Measurement of water absorbancy :

For the measurement of water absorbancy, samples were cut into pieces of size 4 cm × 4 cm. The samples were soaked in distilled water for about 48 h and were hung in free air for about 40 min to drip out the excess water absorbed by the samples. These samples were then kept on a blotting paper for 5 min to absorb excess water present on the surface of the samples. Now, the weight of the wet samples were taken to find the absorbancy of water by using the following formula :

Note

Water absorbancy, % = $(W_{\text{wet}} - W_{\text{dry}})/W_{\text{dry}} \times 100$

where, W_{wet} = weight of soaked pad, W_{dry} = weight of dried pad.

Measurement of temperature and relative humidity :

The changes in temperature and relative humidity inside the developed chamber was monitored with a hygrometer. Readings were taken at 1 h interval, until a steady state condition was reached. The experiments were conducted in three replicates. The differences in temperature and relative humidity for ambient and chamber were calculated to indicate the level of cooling and humidification.

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